

Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation and Relationship to a Dynamic Periodic Function

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jul. 2, 2019

In a previous note, we argued $W(x)$, the time-independent bound state wavefunction, mimicked $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle wavefunction in the sense that $d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx)$ is replaced with $d/dx W(x) = \langle ip \text{ conditional} \rangle W(x)$ with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p \text{ } \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$. In this note, we wish to examine if this idea carries over the time-dependent case, namely we wish to consider $d/dx W(x,t)$ to see if too is related in an average sense to $d/dt \exp(ipx - iEt)$.

Conditional Probability

It was argued in a previous note (1), that $W(x)$, the wavefunction which appears as a normalization constant in conditional probability statements, transforms in space like $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle wavefunction, with p replaced by $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$. It was further argued that $W(x)$ is therefore important in quantum mechanics because of its similar behaviour to $\exp(ipx)$.

$$P(p/x) = \int p \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here, the idea is that if one places a quantum particle, described by $\exp(ipx)$ in a region with a potential $V(x)$, it is scattered into various states of this type, each with a weight f_p i.e. $\text{Sum over } p \int p \exp(ipx)$. This expression is $W(x)$, the wavefunction, and it transforms in space like $\exp(ipx)$ except that p is replaced with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$.

A question immediately arises as to the behaviour of the time dependent portion. The free particle wavefunction contains both space and time portions, i.e. $\exp(ipx - iEt)$. This has the math form of a wave as a constant phase is obtained by having $p dx - E dt = 0$. This yields a phase velocity and a wave view of regarding $\exp(ipx - iEt)$. $W(x)$ for a bound state mimics $\exp(ipx - iEt)$, but not as a "wave".

For $W(x)$, there is a factor $\exp(iEt)$, but $W(x)$ does not have a wave structure like $\exp(ipx - Et)$. A small spatial change leads to $d/dx W(x) = \langle ip \text{ conditonal} \rangle W(x)$ while a small time displacement leads to $d/dt W(t) = iE W(x)$. E , which is an average energy (the energy eigenvalue) seems to be the average speed with which $W(x)$ moves through time. E is a constant while $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is a function of x . $\exp(iEt)$ for $W(x,t)$ seems to indicate there is a kind of cycling occurring in time. This cycling appears to be related to the fact that $\exp(ipx)$ is scattering into many different "p" states within a certain amount of time and should be periodic. E is called an average energy (even though it is an eigenvalue) because all possible "p" states are included in $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and $\langle p^*p \text{ conditional} \rangle$. In fact, $1/2m \langle p^*p \text{ conditional} \rangle = .5 m v(x)v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity which satisfies $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ may be linked to E in the following manner:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = V(x) - \frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle - \frac{1}{2}m \langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle^2 \quad ((2))$$

Thus, a simple wave type motion is not present, but considering space and time separately, $W(x)$ does seem to mimic $\exp(ipx - iEt)$, but with averages instead of p and $p^2/2m$.

To see the cycling behaviour of the quantum bound state in time, consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation, with $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ both replaced by Fourier series. This leads to:

$$p^2/2m f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = E f_p \quad ((3))$$

which has the appearance of a cycling equation with $E f_p$ taking the role of $i \frac{d}{dt} f_p(t)$ or $f_p(t) = \exp(iEt)$ for all p . Thus, even though each p is related to $\exp(ipx)$, all have the same time dependence, namely $\exp(iEt)$.

Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation

The question now becomes what to do in the time dependent case. If one argues that $W(x,t)$ should still mimic $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, but not in a wave sense, rather in the sense that there is a speed in time i.e. that $\frac{d}{dt} W(x,t)$ has a certain behaviour. One may first choose a fixed x point, say x_0 , and expand:

$W(x_0,t) = \sum_{t} b(x_0,t) \exp(iEt)$ as a Fourier series. Here both positive and negative E values are allowed.

In such a case, one is creating a conditional average in time, with time having two probability channels, like $\exp(ipx)$, namely $\cos(Et)$ and $\sin(Et)$. In fact, we suggest this may be the idea associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(iEt)$ rather than strict wave motion.

For the time-dependent case, like in the classical case, there is still an average energy at a point x at time t . We argue that it may still be given by:

$$\text{Energy average}(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2}m \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) \right] / W(x) + V(x)$$

One may try to equate this with

$$\langle i E \text{ conditional} \rangle = \left[\sum_{E} iE b_n(x,t) \exp(iEt) \right] / W(x,t)$$

In a similar manner to $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$, this leads to:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = \text{Energy average}(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2}m \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) \right] / W(x) + V(x) \quad ((4))$$

Conclusion: Connection with $\exp(ipx-iEt)$

Thus, it seems one begins in quantum mechanics with $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, but instead of interpreting this as wave motion, one considers that momentum and energy both have two probability channels (which average separately) with periodic motion linking the two i.e. $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ and $\cos(Et) + i \sin(Et)$. One does not need to link momentum and energy in order to describe space-time motion with a particle at a specific x at a time t . Momentum is linked to speed in space and energy to time. For a bound particle, one considers all possible momenta and a conditional average of ip or $[d/dx W] / W$ yields momentum flow. The second spatial derivative yields $(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W] / W$ which is equivalent to classical kinetic energy $.5mv(x)v(x)$. Average energy is constant at each point x , but there is still energy cycling, or the two channels $\cos(Et)$ and $i \sin(Et)$.

In the time-dependent case, one allows for full conditional averaging in time i.e. $[\text{Sum over } E \text{ } b(x,t) \exp(iEt)] / W(x,t)$ which is equivalent to $i [d/dt W(x,t)] / W(x,t)$. This yields an average energy such that $d/dt W(x,t) = \langle i E \text{ conditional} \rangle W(x,t)$, so that $W(x,t)$ changes in t space like $\exp(iEt)$, but with E replaced with the conditional average. In p space, at a fixed t point, it changes like $d/dx W(x,t) = \langle i p \text{ conditional at } t \rangle W(x,t)$. For the bound state case, $\langle i E \text{ conditional} \rangle$ becomes a single E eigenvalue and density $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ becomes $W(x)W(x)$ and does not change in time, even though there is still energy cycling or the two probability channels for energy $\cos(Et)$ and $i \sin(Et)$. For the bound state, a resonance occurs which does not allow density to change in time. In the case of classical statistical mechanics, one only deals with density $f(p,x)$, but it seems cycling is also occurring, although it may not be of the form $\cos(Et)$ and $i \sin(Et)$. For the case of the ground state oscillator, quantum mechanics yields a density of the same form as classical statistical mechanics for the same problem, even though $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ exists for the quantum case and not the classical.

It is interesting to note that in analysing $W(x,t)$, one may choose a specific time t_0 , and then take a Fourier transform of $W(x,t)$ to describe it in terms of plane waves $\exp(ipx)$, or choose a specific x_0 , and expand in terms of $\exp(iEt)$ to consider an independent averaging of the two energy probability channels. This is unusual because for the time-independent problem one writes $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$. f_p does not depend on time directly, but the idea is that during a cycle of time $1/E$, the quantum particle is scattered from one p state into another, with f_p being the weights. Thus, time is in the picture. For $W(x,t)$, the time dependent case, at a given instant t , it seems that there is a set of weights f_p , but one might argue that the particle can only be in one of them. This begs the question of how one should obtain f_p experimentally? It seems that one would have to consider an ensemble of systems. In the time independent case, one could consider an ensemble, or sample many times within the time period $1/E$ (assuming measurements which did not disrupt the system.) Such a state would have an energy of $p^2/2m + V(x)$ at x . Alternatively, one has different weights to be in a certain energy state obtained by evaluating $W(x,t)$ at x_0 and expanding in $\exp(iEt)$. These issues may indicate that in quantum mechanics, it does make sense to analyze a point x at a time t too closely. The quantum

particles themselves may have a “length” related to the wavelength, implying that time would most likely also not be sharp (i.e. at the point level), but also be related to an interval.

References

Ruggeri, Francesco R. Wavefunction and it Relationship to a Dynamic Periodic Function (preprint, zenodo, 2019)